

The Main Directions of Cooperation of the Prevention Inspector with the Labor Authorities

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The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" defines as the goal of the prevention of offenses the maintenance and strengthening of law and order, the detection and elimination of violations, the determination and elimination of the causes of violations and the conditions that allow them to occur. shown ¹.

The purpose of the labor bodies as a body that directly implements the prevention of violations is to ensure the safety of the population, to regulate the relations between the population and the employer. identifying vacant jobs in local areas, as well as taking measures to provide them with the necessary employees, maintaining and strengthening law and order in this regard, involving the general public in the prevention of offenses, improving the legislation on labor authorities, legal awareness of the population in this regard and improving culture, preventing crimes and antisocial behavior, identifying and eliminating them, determining the reasons for their occurrence and the conditions that enable them, keeping records of unemployed people and vacancies, analysis to make and develop measures to fill them consists of output and implementation.

Employment consists of a system of organizational, economic and legal measures aimed at providing employment to the population .

As a subject of crime prevention, the main characteristics of labor bodies and their content are based on concepts in scientific theoretical literature and within the framework of the law .

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Offenses" specifies a number of powers of labor bodies in the field of prevention of offenses and consists of the following:

crime prevention programs participates in development and implementation;

labor and population employment develops, approves and implements crime prevention programs;

population work with provide measures sees takes account of the unemployed and implements social support measures for the unemployed;

labor and population employment implements the prevention of violations, including identifying and eliminating the causes of these violations and the conditions that make them possible;

cooperates with other bodies and institutions that directly implement ²crime prevention and participate in it.

¹ of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2014 Law "On Prevention of Offenses". "Justice"-2021.

² Uzbekistan Republic of 2014 year 14 in May Article 15 of the Law on Prevention of Offenses. "Justice"-2021.

Our analysis of scientific literature and law violations the subject of prevention as work shows that the organs are not fully and perfectly described. In this regard, ZS Zaripov and I. Ismailov directly implemented the prevention of violations increasing subject by social variety of life determining its causes and conditions, other determinants in the fields and eliminating them achieve effect loss, weakening They described it as the activity of implementing measures .³A direct implementer of crime prevention as a subject work bodies description in lighting to the following attention should be paid to:

- To the content of the activity of labor bodies as a subject that directly implements the prevention of offenses;
- The purpose of the activity of labor bodies as a subject that directly implements the prevention of offenses, tasks and directions;
- To the mutual cooperation of the labor bodies as a subject that directly implements the prevention of offenses;
- To the activity of early prevention of violations of the activity of labor bodies as a subject that directly implements the prevention of violations;
- The basis and procedure for the application of measures by labor bodies as the subject directly implementing the prevention of offenses;
- The entity that directly implements crime prevention as work organs offenses specific aspects of adherence to preventive principles in prevention;
- To the legal bases regulating the activity of labor bodies as a subject directly implementing the prevention of crimes.

It is appropriate to define the tasks of labor bodies as the subject directly implementing the prevention of offenses as follows:

- Social problems solution reach;
- Development of legal documents related to providing the population with useful work, changes and additions to the existing ones ;
- Employment is aimed at increasing the legal awareness and culture of the population in the relationship between the employer and the employee. development and implementation of measures;
- Reasons for committing crimes related to unemployment and theirs identify enabling conditions, empty development and implementation of employment and unemployment accounting, analysis and measures;
- Supervision, coordination and methodical support of the activity of labor bodies as a subject that directly implements the prevention of offenses;
- Organizing activities aimed at providing employment to the population in various forms through the existing unemployed population in the population employment⁴¹⁸.

Article 9 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" directly implements the prevention of offenses the system of bodies and institutions has been determined, and

³ Zaripov ZS, Ismailov I. Criminology: General part. Textbook / yu.fd, prof. Under the editorship of G. Abdumajidov. - T., Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1996- 227 p.

⁴ Zakirova AG Jealousy because of happened done to crimes against struggle problems. YU.fd dis. Autoref. - T., 2004. - B. 41.

the fact that labor bodies have been included in this line indicates the incomparable role of labor bodies in the implementation of crime prevention. It is a pity that most of the crimes are committed among young people, but in order to prevent such crimes among young people, measures are being taken to improve the living environment of the population, to spend their free time effectively. cooperation with labor authorities is used in practice for the implementation of such tasks.

"We are "Justice the law priority" said principle based on this, we will vigorously continue our work aimed at strengthening the sense of respect for the law and intolerance to violations in our society. In this regard, special attention is paid to the prevention of violations. For this, first of all , we need to take measures ⁵to widely use the opportunities of the neighborhood, increase the work efficiency and responsibility of prevention inspectors, and create decent service and living conditions for them .

These, in turn, are violations prevention directly done increasing as a subject work organs activities efficient organize reach and him implementation with depends tasks high level to perform just like that is enough. Internal affairs agencies in the country by administrative territorial unit, some in the regions, districts and in cities criminogenic situation complete learns there is forces and means of preventing and eliminating violations use efficiency analysis does. As a result of the analysis strength and of means distribution situation and this in the field there is has been problem and shortcomings determines them elimination on the surface measures work comes out and done increases.

Internal affairs organs of offenses general , special , individual in order and victimological prevention done increases . Especially violations happened to be done reasons and to them possibility giving condition - conditions determines and them eliminate reach according to suggestion , recommendation and prophylactic action - actions work comes out as well their done increase provides

Prevention (senior) by inspectors of offenses alone in order prevention measures done increase order that in chapter 9 named defined in order basically internal affairs organs six category to individuals relatively prophylactic account their work they walk Prophylactic account from getting intended main goal alone in order prophylactic effect show through person morally correction , in the future offense happened of arrival prevention get is considered⁶

One of the main factors that negatively affects the effectiveness of combating crime, in particular, their detection, and creates conditions for the continuation of the criminal activity of criminals, is artificially stopping the growth of statistical indicators of crime (non-detection of committed crimes , non-registration) is considered. Effective measures to eliminate such negative situations view, in particular, statistical reports on crime rates in keeping internal affairs at the initiative of the authorities highlighting the identified crimes and increasing detection of such crimes to go positive price to give and to encourage directed it is desirable to implement a new way of working. Prevention of violations in this and tasks such as activation of involvement in social and useful activities among the population, increasing the effectiveness of measures on the effective and meaningful organization of free time of minors are considered a priority task.

⁵ Shaukat Mirziyoyev. "The law priority and a person interests provision is a pledge of the country's development and people's well-being". Adopted the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan of being done 24 anniversary dedicated in the ceremony lecture./People word., 2016., No. 243(6678) B.1-3.

⁶ Scientific-practical review of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Offenses": Commentary on the Law / Authors' team. Responsible editor ASTursunov. - T.: Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. - B.29.

As the head of our state said, "... it is necessary to abandon the practice of chasing numbers. People will agree with you if you solve a few problems in practice rather than hundreds of problems solved on paper. The most important thing is that our people know about the changes in the state, the state authority in the system in reality too own representative that there is should feel. Otherwise, all our work and activities will be wasted ⁷. " The same At the moment, the rating system shows how someone is working, their talent, what they are capable of, and their professional skills. It can be seen from these statements that every person should perform his labor activity based on his mental capacity.

First of all, it is necessary to organize the cooperation of the labor bodies as a subject directly implementing the prevention of offenses in the implementation of the activities of prevention of offenses and combating crime with self-government bodies of citizens and other institutions of civil society. After all, they are well aware of the criminal situation in the neighborhood, as well as the individual business entities in the neighborhood and the vacancies that are introduced by them.

The main factor of ensuring the rule of law is not the effective organization of crime prevention and the fight against the causes of crime, but the condition leading to it - is to identify and eliminate conditions in time.

Based on the powers specified in the law, labor bodies develop state programs for the prevention of violations participates in output and implementation. For that matter they are participates by making proposals and recommendations on state crime prevention programs or presenting projects of state crime prevention programs. Also, based on the analysis of the existing criminogenic situation and the causes and conditions of crime within the framework of the powers of the prosecutor's office system (in the republic, region, district (city) section) or approved in connection with the prevention of offenses state or regional programs performance develops, approves and ensures the implementation of sectoral programs on crime prevention in order to ensure . also the law in the documents defined authority within labor and population social protection to do of offenses reason and based on the analysis of the conditions or to ensure the implementation of state or regional programs approved in connection with the prevention of offenses, develops job creation parameters from the data on the number of unemployed and underemployed, makes corrections to them, and regional employment evaluates the implementation of programs and develops social support measures for the population and ensures their implementation.

The entity that directly implements crime prevention the following should be defined as the main directions of activity of labor bodies:

Development and implementation of measures to improve law enforcement practice and legislation first of all, in order to prevent and put an end to the population, especially among minors and young people, to ensure their employment, as well as to identify, analyze and eliminate the causes and conditions of their occurrence, analysis and elimination increase efficiency ;

Strengthening public control, development of social and public-private partnership, self-government bodies of citizens and citizenship of society another institutions establish direct cooperation with; actively cooperate with the neighborhood, constantly studying the meaning and significance of the implemented preventive measures , the level of their need for work with the population ;

to increase the efficiency of crime prevention by providing the population with jobs, including the dynamics of crimes committed by the unemployed, the frequency of their commission, social opinion, citizens' satisfaction with the results of preventive works, and specific evaluation criteria that take into account the level of cooperation with the population current reach;

⁷ Uzbekistan Republic President Shavkat Mirziyoyev High To the meeting Address // People's word.-2017.-23 December'.

of offenses , to ensure that addressability, industry specialization, regional and other specific features are taken into account in the development and implementation of interdepartmental programs for labor bodies;

social problems solution achieve the first in line population to ensure employment, to activate the involvement of women and young people in socially useful activities, to increase the effectiveness of measures and measures to meaningfully organize free time of minors;

regular work dealing with improving the mechanisms of involvement of citizens and public organizations in relation to individuals, including by encouraging them by paying for their work in material and other ways ⁸.

of cooperation main directions in the following manifestation will be:

- Internal affairs bodies, social protection of labor and population, departments with together, also in the area to the employment of minors and young people who need employment after graduating from vocational colleges, academic lyceums and high schools in the service area agreed with the management of organizations and institutions, farms, various businesses and medium-sized enterprises help shows. That's it for the purpose of prevention inspector internal affairs bodies base point In his passport, he records information about the addresses, phone numbers, managers and available jobs of enterprises, institutions and organizations located in the territory, and from time to time with changes and additions to this information.
- prevention of the protection of the rights and freedoms of minors working in enterprises, institutions and organizations inspectors territorial prosecutor's office organs, work and conducts inspections in the places where they serve together with the employees of the social protection bodies of the population. In such inspections, minors should not be allowed to work in hard working conditions, in situations that pose a risk to their health, in night shifts. will take measures in this regard makes submissions of appropriate content to eliminate identified deficiencies;
- The internal affairs bodies assist the social protection bodies of the district and city labor bodies in helping citizens engage in small business and private entrepreneurship, supporting their initiatives in this regard;
- Social protection of district and city labor bodies of internal affairs bodies to do by the authorities assists them in carrying out appropriate campaigning and promotion work on social protection of the population and assistance in providing them with work with the help of local mass media and visual advertisements ;

To conclude, further improvement of the activities of labor bodies as a subject of crime prevention, coordination and control doer directly done increasing and in it Based on the characteristics of the participating bodies and institutions, it is appropriate to clearly classify them in the law.

⁸ Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of crime prevention and combating crime" dated March 14, 2017 PQ-2833 // URL: